

Supplemental Table S1. Behavior monitoring ear tag (SenseHub, Merck Animal Health) complete (1440 min) active days for all calves. Calves were tagged in the right ear on d 3 ± 2 (mean \pm SD; range: d 0-7) of life. “First day tag was active” was considered the first full day the tag recorded after the tag was applied, or the first full day a tag reported a “low activity” percentage lower than 80% after birth. “Low activity” values higher than 80% were considered to reflect time when the tag was active but not yet applied to the calf, or had not yet registered the calf’s movement correctly. Tags collected behavioral data continuously from this starting point until the start of weaning, or until the tag failed, whichever came first. In some cases, tags began recording a few days after birth, and failed before weaning.

Year	Calf	Treatment	First day tag was active	Last day tag was active	Total number of days tag recorded	Ideal number of days tag would have recorded	% of data collection period with active tag ¹
2018	2933	Hay	4	49	46	50	92
2018	2934	Control	2	49	48	50	96
2018	2935	Hay	2	49	48	50	96
2018	2936	Control	2	50	49	51	96
2018	2937	Hay	2	50	49	51	96
2018	2938	Control	2	50	49	51	96
2018	2939	Hay	4	50	47	51	92
2018	2940	Control	4	50	47	51	92
2018	2941	Hay	2	48	47	49	96
2018	2942 ²	Control	NA	NA	NA	51	0
2018	2943	Hay	1	49	49	50	98
2018	2944	Control	2	49	48	50	96
2018	2945	Hay	2	50	49	51	96
2018	2946	Hay	8	49	42	50	84
2018	2947	Hay	4	48	45	49	92
2018	2948	Control	4	48	45	49	92
2018	2949	Control	3	49	47	50	94
2018	2950	Control	1	48	48	49	98
2018	2951	Hay	2	49	48	50	96
2018	2952	Control	1	49	49	50	98
2018	2953	Control	8	48	41	49	84
2018	2954	Hay	3	48	46	49	94
2019	3017	Control	2	37	36	50	72
2019	3019	Hay	2	33	32	50	64
2019	3022	Hay	2	35	34	50	68
2019	3023	Hay	1	37	37	50	74
2019	3024	Hay	2	37	36	50	72

2019	3025	Hay	2	34	33	50	66
2019	3026	Control	2	34	33	50	66
2019	3027	Hay	1	32	32	50	64
2019	3028	Hay	6	43	38	50	76
2019	3029	Control	3	32	30	50	60
2019	3030	Hay	3	28	26	50	52
2019	3031	Control	4	40	37	50	74
2019	3032	Hay	4	30	27	50	54
2019	3033	Control	8	44	37	50	74
2019	3034	Hay	2	33	32	50	64
2019	3035	Hay	1	18	18	50	36
2019	3036	Control	2	18	17	50	34
2019	3037	Hay	2	30	29	50	58
2019	3038	Hay	2	26	25	50	50
2019	3039	Control	2	29	28	50	56
2019	3040	Hay	3	17	15	50	30
2019	3041	Hay	3	33	31	50	62
2019	3042	Control	3	33	31	50	62
2019	3043	Hay	4	26	23	50	46
2019	3044	Control	2	38	37	50	74
2019	3045 ³	Hay	4	10	7	50	14
2019	3046	Hay	6	34	29	50	58

¹Percentage of the data collection period (birth to start of weaning) that was covered by active, recording tags; collection ended when calves began step-down weaning, which was at d 49 to 51 in 2018 and d 50 in 2019.

²Removed from analysis due to complete tag failure

³Removed from analysis for having < 2 weeks of complete rumination data

Supplemental Table S2. Model-predicted probabilities and means and test statistics from hurdle models evaluating the effect of hay provision on the onset of grain and water intake and rumination in individually housed Holstein heifer calves fed milk replacer, water, and grain (Control, n = 20) and mountaingrass hay (Hay, n = 29).

Outcome	Threshold	Likelihood of not reaching threshold		ZI model ¹		Age at reaching threshold (d) ²				Conditional model ⁴					
		Estimated marginal probability ± SE		Treatment		Treatment		Year		Treatment		Year		Treatment*Year	
		Control	Hay	X ² ₁	P-value	Control	Hay	2018	2019	X ² ₁	P-value	X ² ₁	P-value	X ² ₁	P-value
Rumination ⁴	5%	5.3 ± 5.1%	0.0 ± 0.0%	0.000	0.998	14.9 ± 1.3	11.8 ± 0.9	.	.	3.907	0.048
	10%	21.1 ± 9.4%	7.1 ± 4.9%	1.807	0.179	17.3 ± 1.7	16.6 ± 1.3	.	.	0.109	0.742
	15%	47.4 ± 11.5%	10.7 ± 5.8%	6.946	0.008	20.1 ± 2.2	20.4 ± 1.4	.	.	0.020	0.887
	20%	94.7 ± 5.1%	39.3 ± 9.2%	9.176	0.002
Grain	50 g	12.5 ± 1.4	12.2 ± 1.2	.	.	0.031	0.861
	100 g	19.6 ± 2.2	19.2 ± 1.8	.	.	0.021	0.884
	250 g	25.0 ± 9.7%	13.8 ± 9.7%	0.968	0.325	32.4 ± 1.5	30.8 ± 1.1	34.2 ± 1.4	29.3 ± 1.2	0.568	0.451	3.309	0.069	0.037	0.848
	500 g	70.0 ± 10.2%	44.8 ± 10.2%	2.948	0.086	39.7 ± 2.6	40.3 ± 1.7	44.4 ± 2.4	36.1 ± 2.0	0.179	0.672	1.840	0.175	0.156	0.693
	900 g	95.0 ± 4.9%	82.8 ± 4.9%	1.462	0.227
Water	1 L	2.5 ± 1.0	1.3 ± 0.9	.	.	0.798	0.372
	2 L	0.0 ± 0.0%	3.4 ± 3.4%	0.000	0.998	3.6 ± 2.8	7.5 ± 2.5	.	.	0.782	0.377
	3 L	10.0 ± 6.7%	24.1 ± 7.9%	1.488	0.223	24.5 ± 4.1	16.3 ± 3.1	.	.	2.771	0.096
	4 L	45.0 ± 11.1%	44.8 ± 9.2%	0.000	0.990	29.5 ± 5.7	26 ± 4.5	.	.	0.249	0.618
	5 L	75.0 ± 9.7%	65.5 ± 8.8%	0.498	0.481	26.5 ± 6.9	27.0 ± 5.0	.	.	0.003	0.956

¹Model component that used a logistic regression to evaluate whether access to hay affected the probability of reaching each target threshold. The ZI term was only included in the model when the dataset included at least 1 zero value.

²Of the calves that successfully reached the threshold.

³Model component that uses data from successful onsets to evaluate whether access to hay influenced the age at which target thresholds were reached. This component was only evaluated when n (calves reaching the threshold) ≥ 2/treatment

⁴Rumination data are based on 19 Control and 28 Hay calves due to missing data

Supplemental Figure S1. Proportion of a 24-h d engaged in rumination obtained through live observations using 1-0 sampling at 5-s intervals compared with behavior monitoring accelerometer ear tags (SenseHub, Merck Animal Health). The red line represents a perfect relationship (coefficient of determination = 1, slope = 1, intercept = 0) and the dotted line represents the estimate generated by the tag comparison. Each point represents an individual calf. For inclusion in this comparison, tag data needed to represent a complete (1440 min) day on the same day as a live observation and had to have < 80% of time spent in the “low activity” category (only occurred between d 0-7 and considered to reflect an active tag that was not yet on a calf). This resulted in 16 calves from 2019 who were observed in wk 4 of life. Detailed information about live observations is available in Downey and Tucker (2023). Using the *linearHypothesis* function in R (package “car” version 3.1-3; Fox and Weisberg, 2019), the intercept of the estimate (0.02) was found to not be significantly different from 0 ($P = 0.445$), and the slope of the estimate (1.22) was not significantly different from 1 ($P = 0.100$). The adjusted coefficient of determination (R^2) was 0.86.

Downey, B. C. and C. B. Tucker. 2023. Providing long hay in a novel pipe feeder or a bucket reduces abnormal oral behaviors in milk-fed dairy calves. *J. Dairy Sci.* 106:1968-1985. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2022-22413>.

Fox, J. and S. Weisberg. 2019. *An R Companion to Applied Regression*. 3rd ed. SAGE, Thousand Oaks, CA. <https://socialsciences.mcmaster.ca/jfox/Books/Companion>.